

Supplemental Methods

Sample processing.

Total RNA was extracted from whole blood collected into PAXgene RNA stabilization vacutainers and processed using a standard protocol (Qiagen, USA). (Kober, Dunn, et al., 2016) RNA concentration was measured by NanoDrop UV spectrophotometry (ThermoScientific, USA).

Microarray hybridization.

Approximately 100 nanograms (ng) of total RNA was prepared using the Illumina Total Prep RNA Amplification Kit (Ambion, USA) and hybridized to the HumanHT-12 v4.0 Expression BeadChip (47,214 transcripts) (Illumina, USA). BeadChips were scanned using the iScan system (Illumina, USA) at the University of California, San Francisco Genomics Core Facility. (Kober, Dunn, et al., 2016) Each HumanHT-12 BeadChip contained 12 sample BeadArrays.

Microarray data preprocessing and normalization.

Summary level data were calculated from the uncorrected, non-normalized, and non-transformed summary intensities at the probe level with GenomeStudio (Illumina, San Diego, CA). Data preparation and analyses were performed in R (Version 3.3.3) using well-established protocols. (Butte, 2002; Gentleman et al., 2004; Reimers, 2010; Ritchie, Dunning, Smith, Shi, & Lynch, 2011) The quality control procedures were described in detail previously. (Kober, Dunn, et al., 2016) Two arrays were excluded because of poor hybridization performance for positive, background negative, and biotin controls assays. The remaining arrays displayed no unusual distance signal intensity distributions with ArrayQualityMetrics.(Kauffmann, Gentleman, & Huber, 2009; Kauffmann & Huber, 2010) Background correction, quantile normalization, and \log_2 transformation were performed using limma. (Smyth, 2005) Probes with insufficient expression measurements (Illumina Detection p-value <0.05) were excluded. Surrogate variable analysis (SVA, version 3.22.0) (Leek & Storey, 2007) was used to identify technical variations (e.g., potential batch effects).

Procedures for DNA Processing to Obtain Methylation Data

Biospecimen processing.

DNA were archived from buffy coats using the PUREGene DNA isolation kit (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) as previously described.(Aouizerat et al., 2015; Dhruva et al., 2015) DNA samples were quantitated with the NanoDrop UV spectrophotometer (ThermoScientific, USA) and normalized to a concentration of 50 ng/microliter (μL).

Microarray hybridization.

DNA methylation state was measured with the HumanMethylation450K (Illumina, San Diego, CA) microarray. BeadChips were scanned using the iScan system (Illumina, San Diego, CA) at the University of California, San Francisco Genomics Core Facility. This array contains >450,000 methylation sites located at regions of DNA where a cytosine nucleotide is flanked in the 5' direction by a guanine nucleotide (i.e., CpG site).

Multi-staged methylation loci selection.

The multi-staged analysis requires selection of the methylation loci located in regulatory regions of the differentially expressed genes from the >450,000 methylation loci interrogated by the HumanMethylation450K microarray. Differentially expressed candidate genes were located on the reference human genome. Transcript microarray probes identified as differentially expressed in the gene expression analysis were mapped to genes and the associated RefSeq identifier (Pruitt, Tatusova, Brown, & Maglott, 2012) using the annotation provided by Illumina (San Diego, CA) for the HumanHT V4 microarray (version HumanHT-12_V4_0_R1_15002873_B). Then, because methylation can inhibit transcription through alterations in TFBS, (Jones, 2012) we limited our selection of probes to those that were located in these regions. The methylation array probes in TFBS regions for these genes that were available on the HumanMethylation450K were identified using the “IlluminaHumanMethylation450kprobe” annotation data (<http://bioconductor.org>). Methylation loci were identified in putative TFBS defined as 8,000 bases upstream and 2,000 bases downstream of the transcript start site for the gene based on the RefSeq gene model. (Koudritsky & Domany, 2008) Probes identified from the putative TFBS region for each candidate gene and the microarray control probes were included in the analyses.

The reference human genome assembly (Genome Reference Consortium GRCh37) and regional annotations (e.g., CpG islands) used in this study were obtained using the University of California Santa Cruz (UCSC) Human Genome Browser hg19 (<http://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTracks?db=hg19>). (Rhead et al., 2010) Potential regulatory involvement of each methylation locus was investigated using the ENCODE data tracks for gene regulation. (Consortium et al., 2012; Friedman, Farh, Burge, & Bartel, 2009; Grimson et al., 2007; Lewis, Burge, & Bartel, 2005)

Microarray data preprocessing and normalization.

Uncorrected, non-normalized, non-balanced, and non-transformed microarray data were obtained using GenomeStudio (Illumina, San Diego, CA). Data preparation and analyses were done using well-established protocols in R. (Bock, 2012) Corrections for Infinium I and II probes, balance correction, background correction, and quantile normalization were performed using the minfi BioConductor package in R. (Aryee et al., 2014; Du, Kibbe, & Lin, 2008) Probes that contain a single nucleotide polymorphism at a CpG or flanking site, and probes that aligned to multiple places on the genome were excluded. (Chen et al., 2013) Methylation scores were quantified as beta levels (β -value). Because DNA methylation differs between blood cell types, (Koestler et al., 2013) SVA was used to evaluate methylation data and control for potential cell type heterogeneity and for batch effects. (Houseman, Molitor, & Marsit, 2014; McGregor et al., 2016)

Data Analyses

Latent profile analysis (LPA).

The method used to identify the evening fatigue latent classes was described in detail previously. (Kober, Cooper, et al., 2016) Briefly, LPA was used to identify subgroups of patients (i.e., latent classes) with distinct evening fatigue trajectories over two cycles of CTX. Of the 582 patients included in the LPA, 20.0% (n=116) were in the Moderate, 21.8% (n=127) were in the High, and

58.2% (n=339) were in the Very High evening fatigue classes. For this paper, comparisons were made between the patients with breast cancer in the Moderate (n=7) and Very High (n=29) evening fatigue classes who had both gene expression and methylation data available.

Demographic and clinical data.

Demographic and clinical data were analyzed using SPSS version 23 (IBM, Armonk, NY). Independent sample t-tests, Mann-Whitney U tests, Chi square tests, and Fisher's Exact tests were used to evaluate for differences in demographic and clinical characteristics between the Moderate and Very High evening fatigue classes.

Differential gene expression.

Differential expression of genes between the latent classes was examined with an estimation of gene-by-gene variance using the limma package for R (version 3.30.13). (Ritchie et al., 2015) Demographic and clinical characteristics and surrogate variables were evaluated as potential covariates in the models. Adjustment for multiple comparisons was performed using the Benjamini and Hochberg method (Hochberg & Benjamini, 1990) with a false-discovery rate (FDR) cutoff of 10%.

Differential methylation.

Tests for differentially methylated probes (DMPs) between classes were done using an F-test implemented in the minfi package for R (version 1.20.2). (Aryee et al., 2014) In addition to single locations, DNA methylation can occur in regions with broad regulatory functions. (Portela & Esteller, 2010) For example, short CpG-rich regions of DNA (CpG islands) are enriched in approximately half of annotated genes and this regional methylation can block initiation of transcription, stimulate elongation, or impact splicing. (Jones, 2012) While some of these regions were identified previously (e.g., CpG islands), newer methods allow for the dynamic identification of regions of biological interest based on observations of methylation state provided by a data set. (Deaton & Bird, 2011) Differences between the latent classes in the differentially methylated regions (DMRs) were evaluated using bumpHunter for R (version 1.14.0). (Jaffe et al., 2012) The bumpHunter algorithm settings included a difference cutoff of 5% and a maximum gap of 1000 with 1000 permutations. Demographic and clinical characteristics and surrogate variables were evaluated for inclusion as potential covariates in the models. As was done in our previous candidate gene studies, (Alfaro et al., 2014; Aouizerat et al., 2015; Dhruva et al., 2015; Doong et al., 2015; Dunn et al., 2013; Illi et al., 2012; Langford et al., 2015; Langford et al., 2014; McCann et al., 2012; Merriman, Aouizerat, Cataldo, et al., 2014; Merriman, Aouizerat, Langford, et al., 2014; Miaskowski et al., 2015; Miaskowski et al., 2012; Miaskowski et al., 2013; Saad et al., 2014; Stephens et al., 2014) and based on the recommendations in the literature, (Bakan, 1966; Rothman, 1990) the type I error threshold for this exploratory study of differential methylation for both DMPs and DMRs was set at 0.05. Associations between methylation state (β -value) and gene expression levels (i.e., \log_2 transformed, background corrected, normalized intensity values) were assessed using Spearman correlation coefficients. Network interaction representations of genes were explored with the STRING database. (Szklarczyk et al., 2017)

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